

USING MIND MAPS FOR READING COMPREHENSION DEVELOPMENT

Isoeva Begimkhon

Lecturer of Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10818324>

Abstract. *Reading comprehension is a vital skill that plays a significant role in our education and professional lives. It involves understanding and interpreting written information effectively. However, many individuals struggle with retaining and comprehending the content they read, especially in L2. One powerful tool that can greatly enhance reading comprehension is the use of mind maps. Mind maps are visual representations that organize information in a hierarchical and interconnected manner, making it easier to understand and remember key concepts. In this article, we will explore how mind maps can be utilized to improve reading comprehension skills.*

Keywords: *reading comprehension, reading skill in L2, mind maps, organizing information, identifying key concepts, visualization, memory retention, active engagement*

Reading comprehension in a second language (L2) can pose several challenges due to linguistic, cognitive, and cultural factors. Some common difficulties that learners may encounter are limited vocabulary range, complex grammar structures, idioms or figurative language and cultural references or lack of contextual understanding [4]. Though, these challenges are normal and can be overcome with persistent effort, practice, and targeted strategies. One of these most common techniques is utilizing Mind Maps with relevant guidance from language instructors that can provide valuable support in navigating difficulties in understanding texts [5].

Generally, mind maps are graphical representations of ideas, concepts, or information that visually organize and connect various elements. They are powerful tools for brainstorming, note-taking, planning, and organizing thoughts or projects. Mind maps typically start with a central concept or topic, and branches radiate outwards, representing subtopics or related ideas [8]. There are some key features and benefits of implementing Mind Maps while reading:

- **Visualizing Information:** mind maps provide a visual structure that helps readers organize and connect the main ideas and supporting details of a text. By creating a mind map while reading, individuals can visually represent the relationships between different concepts and see the overall structure of the information. This visual representation enhances comprehension by facilitating a clearer understanding of the content.

- **Identifying Key Ideas:** when reading, it's common for readers to get lost in a sea of words [6]. Mind maps offer a solution by allowing readers to extract and highlight the most important ideas from a text. By capturing the main concepts and subtopics in a mind map, readers can quickly identify and focus on the key ideas, making it easier to comprehend the overall message of the text.

- **Organizing Thoughts:** mind maps provide a framework for organizing thoughts and ideas. As readers create a mind map, they can categorize information, group related concepts, and establish connections between different ideas. This process helps readers structure their thoughts and aids in the comprehension of complex information [1]. By organizing thoughts visually, readers can better understand how different elements of the text fit together.

- **Enhancing Memory Retention:** one of the challenges in reading comprehension is retaining the information long-term. Mind maps leverage the power of visual and spatial memory,

making it easier to remember the content. The combination of colors, symbols, and images used in mind maps engages multiple senses, reinforcing memory retention. By reviewing the mind map periodically, readers can reinforce their understanding and recall the information more effectively.

- **Active Engagement:** creating a mind map while reading actively engages the reader in the learning process. It requires active thinking, analysis, and synthesis of the content. This active engagement helps readers stay focused, promotes deeper understanding, and prevents passive reading. By actively interacting with the text through the mind mapping process, readers can significantly improve their comprehension skills [2].

To boost reading skills the process of implementation of mind-maps should go through three main phases [1]:

- **Pre-reading phase:** Before diving into a text, teacher encourages students to create a mind map related to the topic or theme they will be reading about. This can include key ideas, vocabulary words, and any prior knowledge they have. This pre-reading mind map serves as an overview and prepares students for the upcoming text.

- **During-reading phase:** As students read the text, they create a mind map that captures the main ideas, supporting details, and relationships between different concepts. They can use keywords, short phrases, and visual elements to represent the information. This process helps students actively engage with the text and promotes deeper understanding.

- **Post-reading phase:** After students have completed reading, they need to revisit their mind maps and expand on them. They can add additional details, examples, or connections they discovered while reading. This step encourages reflection and allows students to synthesize the information they have learned.

Furthermore, each student may have their own preferred way of creating mind maps and call for flexibility and creativity in their approach. Mind maps can be created by hand on paper or by using digital tools and software depending on the resources available. E-mind mapping is one of the newest types of mapping strategies, that empowers learners critical thinking while perceiving the written information and avoid linear thinking. Mind mapping can also be used for inducing reading comprehension and also maintains learners active and fast to produce the language [7]. Digital mind mapping tools often have collaboration features that enable multiple users to work on the same mind map simultaneously. This makes it easy to brainstorm ideas, collaborate on projects, or share your mind maps with others. By using visuals, keywords, and branches, complex concepts can be simplified and communicated more effectively. This helps to ensure that all participants have a clear understanding of the topics being discussed, reducing misunderstandings and encouraging meaningful contributions.

Improving reading comprehension is a goal shared by many individuals, and mind maps offer an effective strategy to achieve this objective. By visualizing information, identifying key ideas, organizing thoughts, enhancing memory retention, and promoting active engagement, mind maps empower readers to comprehend and retain information more effectively. Whether used in academic studies, professional settings, or personal reading, incorporating mind maps can be a valuable technique to enhance reading comprehension skills and unlock the full potential of the written word. With regular use and refinement of mind mapping techniques, readers can experience significant improvements in their reading comprehension abilities.

REFERENCES

1. Berg, H. (2011). How to use mind-mapping to improve reading comprehension. Retrieved August 2, 2017, from Mapping to Improve Reading Comprehension.
2. Buzan, T. (2005) – “Mind map: The ultimate thinking tool.” London: Thorsons.
3. Casco, M. (2009). The Use of “Mind Maps” in the Teaching of Foreign Languages. XXXV FAAPI Conference Proceedings. Bahía Blanca.
4. Dean (2013) – “Theory of Reading”, cited by Muslaini in Journal of Syiah Kuala University, Banda Aceh "Improving Students' Reading Rate and Comprehension by using Timed Repeated", 8(1), 67- 78
5. Gibbons (2023) - <https://www.proquest.com/openview/2603b010cb163bf89aec7cd536b87081/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=41436>.
6. Gómez, M., & King, G. (2014). Using mind mapping as a method to help ESL/EFL students connect vocabulary and concepts in different contexts. TRILOGÍA. Ciencia, Tecnología y Sociedad, 10, 69-85
7. Haerazi, H., Prayati, Z., & Vikasari, R. M. (2019). Practicing contextual teaching and learning (CTL) approach to improve students' reading comprehension in relation to motivation. English Review: Journal of English Education, 8(1), 139-146.
8. Harmer, J. (2001). The Practice of English Language Teaching (3rd ed.). Harlow: Longman.
9. Khasanova G. K. Features of the student's mental activity //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 27. – С. 34-38.
10. Malekzadeh, B., & Bayat, A. (2015). The Effect of Mind Mapping Strategy on Comprehending Implicit Information in EFL Reading Texts. International Journal of Educational Investigations, 2(3), 81-90.
11. Mcnamara, Danielle S. 2007. Reading Comprehension Strategies. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
12. Murley, D. (2007). Mind-mapping complex information. Illinois: Southern Illinois University School of Law Library.
13. Zhou, S. (2016). Scaffolding Chinese College Students' English Learning through Mind Mapping. International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature (IJSELL), 4(1), 31-35.
14. Джураев Д. У. Социализация молодежи-один из основных принципов политики Узбекистана //Молодой ученый. – 2014. – №. 15. – С. 259-260.
15. Джураев Д. У., Назаров А. А. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ПОЛИЯЗЫЧНОЙ СРЕДЫ В ОТНОШЕНИИ НАЗВАНИЙ ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. В3. – С. 595-598.